

is needed only if severity exceeds 5% diseased leaf area before maximum tillering, in the case of highly susceptible cultivars. This concept was tested under favorable upland conditions using CICA4, a highly susceptible cultivar in Colombia. The experiment was repeated three times

at different periods.

Results showed that one application can be eliminated without serious damage or yield loss to rice (see table). Additional application was required only once.

Results from other experiments showed that application at 50% panicle emergence

of moderately BI-resistant cultivars could be eliminated if the average daily precipitation 10-15 d after flowering is less than 2 or more than 18 mm. Disease severity data indicated that the optimum average daily precipitation during this critical period is about 10 mm. □

Relationship between susceptibility to leaf blast (BI) and panicle BI severity

S. W. Ahn and M. Rubiano, Rice Program, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia

Differences in leaf BI and panicle BI susceptibility in the field may be caused by varying macro- or microclimate conditions during disease development. We studied 15 cultivars with different reactions to leaf and panicle BI at Villavicencio.

Plantings were staggered to synchronize the evaluation of leaf and panicle BI and to eliminate the effect of different weather on BI development. Planting density was higher than normal (200 kg seed/ha) to provide a favorable microclimate for leaf BI development.

There was a highly positive relationship between leaf BI infection level and panicle BI severity (see figure), which shows that cultivars genetically susceptible to a population of certain BI races are susceptible to both leaf and panicle infection.

The frequently observed difference

between leaf and panicle BI reaction in the field may be due to the changes in micro- or macroclimates during distinct growth phases. Generally, the microclimate influence is greater on leaf BI

development than on panicle BI. Changes in the frequency of races in the population of *Pyricularia oryzae* in a crop season could also influence leaf and panicle reaction. □

Relationship between panicle and leaf BI severity. Evaluations were made at the same time and place in synchronized plantings. DAS = days after sowing.

Influence of planting time on blast (BI) incidence

S. Mohan, research associate; P. Vasudevan, associate professor; and B. Gururajan, associate professor, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University Research Centre, Vellore 632001, India

Environmental factors influence the epidemiology of BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*. We studied the influence of environment on BI incidence on IR50, which was recently introduced in North Arcot. IR50 matures early (105 to 110 d) and has high yield potential.

IR50 was transplanted on different dates in 1983 rabi. Total leaves and leaves with spindle-shaped BI spots were counted from 50 randomly selected hills/field at tillering and percent BI incidence was calculated (see table). Minimum and maximum temperatures and relative humidity (RH) were recorded when fields were scored.

Highest BI incidence was in the crop planted in mid-Dec, followed by that planted in early Jan (see table). BI incidence was lowest in the earliest sown crop perhaps because the temperature was higher and RH lower than with the crops sown later. □

Effect of planting time on BI incidence, Vellore, India.

Planting date	Diseased leaves (%)	Max temp (°C)	Min temp (°C)	Relative humidity (%)
25 Oct	3	32.2	22.8	87
18 Nov	51	30.6	20.1	84
5 Dec	62	26.9	19.6	96
17 Dec	85	26.9	19.6	96
3 Jan	71	29.1	17.9	92